

Violent Identity Politics, Internet and Peace in Manipur

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Abstract

The paper examines the violent identity politics by about thirty ethnic/tribal armed groups of Naga-Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes in Manipur hills and their consequences in the society and politics. The unique multi-ethnic-lingual-religious-cultural society of Manipur itself is not the sole cause. Manipur hills have been a conflict and violent prone zone of the world since 1990s before social media revolution. Inability to protect the rights of the citizens and divisive and communal armed identity politics manufacture conflicts and violence. Since unprecedented violence from 3rd May, 2023, internet shut down was imposed but violence and sufferings of the people continued. The paper argues that for peace in Manipur ending the ‘appeasement’ of ethnic/tribal armed groups, enforcing rule of law in Manipur hills and democratic and federal solutions is important.

Keywords: Identity politics, violent prone, rule of law, democratic principles, peace

Introduction

Politics decides issues of the collective life of a country, state or at the local level. However non-political factors including culture, language, geography, identity, economy, ideology and visions of leadership influence politics. Identity politics based on ethnic, community, language, religion etc. is ultimately for political power, community and government resources. It is argued that elites construct ethnicity and nationalism for social and political reasons (Brass, 1994). The emerging identity politics is considered as a major threat to liberal democracy (Fukuyama, 2018). Conflicts and violence on the basis of ethnic, community etc. go on in India. Violent identity politics by the armed groups reject the multiple identities of human beings.

Identity is a complex issue and illusion of a unique and choiceless identity cause various kinds of conflicts and barbarities in the world (Sen, 2006). Manipur hills have about thirty armed groups of Naga-Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes demanding conflicting multiple communal homelands for years. The unprecedented number of

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armed groups and their illegal activities are the primary causes for conflicts, divisions and violence in Manipur hills since 1990s. Failure to punish those involved in crimes and illegal activities as per law in the past is a factor for devastating violence in Manipur since May, 2023. Those who violate laws and the rights of the citizens cannot pretend as national. The violent identity politics is essentially communal and divisive against the equality, freedom and humanity.

Despite suspension of operation, the armed groups of Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes continue illegal activities, extortion and deprivation of political rights of common tribal men and women in Manipur hills. New conflicts and violence in Manipur hills with suffering of common people reflect the conservative and regressive politics for exclusive communal homelands in a multi-ethnic-linguistic-cultural society of Manipur. It is argued that ethno-centrism is a serious disease threatening the foundation of human civilization, therefore needs to go beyond ethno-centrism (Kshetri, 2013). Economic development, or deployment of more security forces or the creation of communal homelands alone cannot resolve unprecedented ethnic violence and tensions in Manipur according to Kshetri.

The internet based social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram etc. are used for political propaganda and mobilization since mid-2000s. social media has instances of misuses, addiction and even make the citizens helpless. The internet and social media became popular in India since 2015. Since 3rd May, 2023 violence in Manipur, fake news, propaganda and instigations were clearly visible and internet shutdown could not stop violence. Since 1990s Manipur hills witnessed conflicts and violence including violent clashes of Naga-Kuki (1992), Kuki-Tamil (1995-Moreh), Kuki-Paite(1997-Churachandpur), Kuki-Meitei (Moreh-2007) etc. before social media revolution.

1. Violent Identity Politics in Manipur Hills since 1990s

Manipur was independent kingdom for centuries, a Princely State with a King during British colonial rule (1891-1947), had democratic government with elected Legislative Assembly and Council of Ministers (1948-1949), a Part C State in 1950, a Union Territory and a State from 1972. During the deprivation of democratic government (1949-1972), the separatist identity politics among Naga-Chin-Kuki began in Manipur hills. The migratory nature of Kukis caused conflicts with the groups in whose land they settled (Haokip, 2011). Mushrooming of new villages and migratory tendency is high among Kukis under the Kuki chieftainship system as permanent individual land ownership rights is absent (Kipgen, 2016). These factors partly explain the involvement of Kukis in conflicts and violence in Manipur hills since 1990s.

Thriving border trade took place at Moreh (border town of Manipur with Myanmar), a major tourist place after India's Look East Policy in the 1990s. Moreh had mixed population of Nagas, Meitei, Tamils and Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes. Absence of effective border management with Manipur's 398 Kms long porous border with Myanmar and frequent military rule and political violence since 1962 and from 2021 facilitated influx of refugees, immigrants etc. to Manipur. Thus, immigrant Kukis are going to become majority over the indigenous Kuki (Singh, 2018). Moreh became only for Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes and border trade is closed after violence since 3rd May, 2023.

Meitei settlement in Khuga River Valley in Churachandpur began since 6th Moirang King Punshiba (236-297 AD); Meitei was the third largest group after Paite and Hmar in 1980 and Meitei population was 15,824 in 1997 in Churachandpur (Toijamba, 2023). After 3rd May, 2023 all Meitei were driven out and any sign of Meitei settlement was erased from Churachandpur, the epicentre of violence and separatist politics among Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes. The 'ethnic cleansing' of Meitei from their ancestral land in Churachandpur was complete while the separatist agenda by armed groups was able to convert into a 'mass movement' after violence since May, 2023. Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups projected themselves as tribal/Christian minority and falsely blamed Meitei (Hindu majority) for the violence. As per 2011 Census in Manipur, the Christian population is 41.29 % and Hindu population is 41.39 % (Singh, 2022). The initial euphoria of achieving 'separate' political Chin-Kuki-Zomi homeland by indulging violence methods died down gradually with time.

The separatist identity politics in Manipur hills have deeper roots in the divisive British colonial legacies. The separatist ethnic identity politics of Nagas and Mizos in neighbouring Assam influence Manipur hills. Under Article 342, the indigenous people of Manipur are fragmented into Non-Scheduled Tribe Meitei and ST Naga-Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes. Naga and Kuki identities constructed by the British colonizers by clubbing hill communities arbitrarily are used in post-colonial period by separatist identity politics. Further Naga-Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes are fragmented into thirty-three ST groups obstructing identity politics of Naga and Chin-Kuki-Zomi.

The critical factor is the role of conservative tribal elites, groups and individual leaders among Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes. Land is owned and controlled by the hereditary village chiefs among the Chin-Kuki tribes (Ngaite, 2004; Haokip, 2009). The separatist identity politics among the Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes is to preserve the primitive birth-based privileges on land and economic and political interests of the hereditary tribal village chiefs and tribal elites in Manipur hills. Thus, the demand for Kuki State was first made in 1960 by the Village elders and village chiefs among the Kukis (Arambam, 2018). It was after the passing

of Manipur Village Authority Act, 1956 which provides the elected village authorities in Manipur hills. Manipur Hills Areas (Acquisition of Chiefs' Rights) Act 1967 has been opposed.

The extension of Manipur Land Revenue and Land Reforms Act, 1960 to hill areas has been stalled by the tribal elites (Singh, 2009). This failure restrains and deprives the hill men and women from enjoying the benefits of land rights while Kuki MLAs are representatives of the Kuki chiefs who own land (Haokip, 2004). It also means that no survey of land, no proper land records and no individual land ownership and also no land revenue from hill areas which is over 90% of total land in Manipur. Failure to implement this Act is a primary cause of illegal activities including deforestation, poppy cultivation, illegal settlements and land disputes in Manipur hills for decades.

2. Manipur Violence, Internet and Social Media since May 2023

Manipur violence since May, 2023 has proved that 'Suspension of Operation' and 'talks' with twenty-five-armed Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups could not bring peace and political solutions. The difference since 3rd May, 2023 violence is that the demands for separatist political status by the armed groups are openly joined by MLAs, civil society groups etc. of Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes. Social media has been used since 3rd May, 2023 violence for propaganda. Thus, despite internet ban in Manipur, the Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups made the video of sexual assault of two women viral forcing the Prime Minister of India to break his silence on Manipur violence before Parliament Session on 20 July, 2023 (the Hindu, 20 July, 2023).

A new history is constructed to provide historical basis for the separate Kuki homeland with expanded territory. In the invented history Kuki rebellion 1917-1919 in Manipur is propagated as *The Anglo-Kuki War, 1917-1919: A Frontier Uprising against the Imperialism during the First World War* and also establishes link with those of Chin Hills of Myanmar (Guite and Haokip, 2021). According to Guite and Haokip this invented history is a 'product' of the Kuki Research Forum, a collegium of Kuki intellectual community with the endorsement of the Kuki Inpi and Kuki Students Organization. The new history go against the established historical account of Kuki Rebellion 1917-1920 in Manipur as a great watershed in the history of Manipur with no link with those of Chin State of Burma (Dena, 1991). The academic projection of Kuki Rebellion 1917-1920 as a war or Kuki war of independence is rejected on the ground that only number of heinous crimes of massacre were committed against the indigenous people of Manipur like Tangkhuls, Kabuis etc. (Rajendra, 2022).

Lies and propaganda were made in demanding Kuki State in Manipur hills to Prime Minister of India on 2nd October, 1995 by mentioning that " The districts of Churachandpur, Chandel and Sadar Hills are occupied

100% by Kukis” (Haokip, 2008 :496). It was made a reality by driving out all Meiteis from Churachandpur, Kangpokpi and Moreh after the May, 2023 violence. Without destroying the composite history and independent kingdom of Manipur Kuki homeland cannot be created so the separatist groups reduce Manipur King to Meitei King or Meitei Chief (Haokip, 2008). History of Manipur is established with written records and indigenous sources including Cheitharol Kumbaba, Royal Chronicle of Manipur Kings which is the important source pre-colonial Manipur history (Singh,2016).

What triggered the violence on 3rd May, 2023 for obvious reasons is of debates and controversies. Understanding the ideology and politics of separatist armed groups and the past events in chronological sequence before 3rd May, 2023 violence is required. Influx of immigrants from Myanmar settled in Tengnoupal, Chandel, Churachandpur, Pherzawl, Senapati, Kangpokpi and even Ukhrul and Kamjong (Singh, 2022). Therefore, any attempt to identify non-native people of Manipur is opposed by Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups which became violent in Churachandpur after the passing the Protection of Manipur People’s Bill, 2015 by Manipur Legislative Assembly with 1951 as the base year.

The BJP led government in Manipur took up series of measures against the illegal drug trade (officially ‘War against Drug’), deforestation and destruction of poppy plantation in the hills. There were protest by the Kuki groups against the eviction of 16 Kuki households by the Government authorities for encroaching protected forest land in K. Songjang village in Churachandpur district on 20 February, 2023 (Hasnat, 2023). Violent protests took place on 28 April, 2023 against the proposed visit of the Chief Minister of Manipur to Churachandpur (the Times of India, 28 April, 2023). The forest office in Churachandpur was burnt on 29 April, 2023 (Leivon, 2023).

One common false narrative in the media on Manipur violence on 3rd May, 2023 is that the protest against the Manipur High Court Order of recommending ST status of Meitei organised by All Tribal Students’ Union, Manipur turned violence (for instance Mohapatra and Das, 2024). Why protest rally turned violent only in Churachandpur and not in Naga areas? The rally was ‘deliberately’ organised on 3rd May, 2023 to get maximum media attention as the Vice President of India was visiting Manipur on the same day. The collective stand of the separatist groups among Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups since 3rd May, 2023 violence is that ‘separate administration’ first and then only ‘peace’ possible. This is one reason for prolonged violence.

India has the highest number of internet shutdowns in the world in 2016-2024 with 58% of the world while Manipur has the longest days of 143 days after the violence since 3rd May, 2023 (Maurya, 2024). The social media had full of false propaganda and narratives to justify the separatist political demands by blaming only the Meitei or State government. Victim cards are played out by separatist Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups despite

committing some of heinous crimes including killing of two students in Churachandpur in July, 2023 and women and children on 11 November, 2024 in Jiribam (a border town with Assam) in cold blooded manners; both were uploaded in social media.

The false propaganda during violence was that land and forest are under the control of Kuki chiefs so no power of the Government to evict the villagers (who encroached forest area) and there is no tribal in the Imphal Valley as on 12 July, 2023; the separate administration is common demand of SoS groups, MLAs and civil society groups (Vaulzang, 2023). Such lie and propaganda were broasted by Youtube News channel and its anchor. But the truth is that Naga and non-Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes remain in Imphal as before 3rd May, 2023 and today also. Online warriors in social media are active in propagating Kuki hills, Kukiland etc. with map projection of Kuki State but without historical and legal basis.

3. Towards Violent Free and Peaceful Manipur

From Manipur experience since 1990s the more violation of Constitution, democratic rights of the citizens, rule of law and democratic and federal principles more conflicts and violence. The appeasement policy of separatist and communal armed groups of Chin-Kuki-Zomi groups is the dominant approach while bypassing the elected MLAs and government and other stakeholders in Manipur in the past and at present.

Internet shutdown does not ensure peace. This is because the ideology and politics of separatist political homelands among Chin-Kuki-Zomi tribes are rooted in divisive British colonial legacies and knowledge system written in English. Absence of physical violence cannot be equated with peace. Falsehood, lies, hatred, abusive languages and propaganda to achieve separatist political status of Chin-Kuki-Zomi (or Kuki-Zo since 2023) are active today in social media. Sufferings of people who are displaced and in relief camps continue along with violation of Article 19 - freedom to move freely by all the citizens including on National Highways since 3rd May, 2023.

For peace the rule of law and presence of police and civil administration in the hill areas to protect life and property of citizens are important. All the stakeholders should be in dialogue process and democratic and federal principles are necessary for conflict resolutions. The more deviation from such process and principles delay to restore peace in Manipur.

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